

Investigating the behavior of the SIGMA1 algorithm for on-the-fly Doppler broadening on GPU with the TRIPOLI-5 Monte Carlo code: preliminary results

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the behavior and performance of the SIGMA1 algorithm for on-the-fly Doppler broadening when executed on Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) within the TRIPOLI-5 Monte Carlo code. A preliminary verification demonstrated that GPU-based calculations, including those performed on single precision floating point operations-oriented architectures, introduce no significant bias in neutron flux estimation when compared with CPU and pretabulated cross-section results. Subsequently, a parametric study was conducted to evaluate the influence of key user-defined parameters — namely, the number of CPU threads, the size of events buffer in event-based transport, and the number of tasks offloaded on GPU — on simulation time, energy consumption, and GPU utilization. Results show that the number of CPU threads has the dominant effect, while the optimal offload size lies around 10^3 tasks, with a complex and non-linear relationship to performance metrics. These preliminary results provide insight into the efficient use of GPU acceleration for on-the-fly Doppler broadening in Monte Carlo simulations and will guide future optimization efforts on HPC clusters equipped with double precision floating point operations-capable GPUs.

Keywords: Monte-Carlo, Doppler Broadening, High Performance Computing, GPU, SIGMA1

1. INTRODUCTION

High Performance Computing (HPC) in nuclear reactor physics aims towards the modeling of full scale nuclear reactor core, while taking coupled multiphysics into account. Among the main effects to consider for high fidelity modeling, thermal-hydraulic feedbacks lead to accounting for spatially varying temperature and density distributions across the reactor core. These temperature fields, not known a priori, have a significant impact on nuclear cross sections and, consequently, on neutron transport calculations.

While relying on pre-tabulated nuclear data offers the best performances (computation time) compared to other methods such as on-the-fly interpolation techniques or on-the-fly Doppler broadening, the need to load nuclear data files for every temperature found in the system would lead to prohibiting memory footprint. To overcome this limitation, interpolation techniques or on-the-fly Doppler broadening algorithms prove to be essential for this kind of application.

Among these, exact on-the-fly Doppler broadening stands out for its ability to accurately represent the temperature dependence of cross sections without approximation errors inherent to interpolation. However, exact broadening is computationally intensive, creating a need for efficient implementations.

Recent advances in heterogeneous computing, especially the growing availability of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) in HPC architectures, present a compelling opportunity. GPUs offer massive parallelism that can be leveraged to accelerate on-the-fly Doppler broadening, making them a practical and scalable solution for high-fidelity Monte Carlo simulations with thermal feedback.

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The TRIPOLI-5 Monte Carlo calculation code [1], co-developed by ASNR (new French nuclear safety authority) and CEA (*Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux énergies alternatives*), and supported by EDF (*Electricité de France*), relies on the SIGMA1 algorithm [2] for on-the-fly Doppler broadening, for which two versions have been implemented: a classical C++ implementation for CPU processing and a CUDA implementation to harvest GPU capabilities [3].

This work presents preliminary results on the performance analysis of the SIGMA1 CUDA implementation in TRIPOLI-5 for different set of GPU related parameters that require to be set in the input model. This type of study aims both to verify the behavior of GPU offloading in TRIPOLI-5 for practical cases and to provide guidance to users on the choice of parameters to obtain the best simulation performance.

2. THE SIGMA1 ALGORITHM

The SIGMA1 algorithm implemented in TRIPOLI-5 follows directly the formulation presented in [2]. It is a method that permits Doppler broadening of cross-section data from a base temperature T_1 to any higher temperature T_2 while preserving the ability to perform linear interpolation of the resulting cross sections. Consequently, one can obtain cross sections at arbitrary temperatures given access to data at a lower temperature (which may even be 0K), making the approach particularly valuable for coupled simulations in which material temperatures are not known a priori. The same method is employed in the NJOY module BROADR for Doppler broadening of cross sections [4].

SIGMA1 relies solely on the deterministic evaluation of integrals, without any stochastic component. This characteristic renders it amenable to vectorization and GPU-based execution. TRIPOLI-5 thus provides two distinct implementations of the algorithm: a CPU-based version written in C++ and a GPU-accelerated version implemented in CUDA. Both implementations adhere to the description in [2], with only minor differences attributable to CUDA syntax and GPU-specific optimizations. The cross sections produced by the two codes agree to machine precision, with negligible discrepancies arising solely from floating-point arithmetic.

3. PRELIMINARY SEARCH OF A POTENTIAL BIAS WHEN USING SINGLE PRECISION SUPPORTING GPU

Only a few GPUs officially support double precision calculations. Three different GPUs have been tested in the frame of this study:

- Nvidia RTX A5000 (Ampere architecture, officially supporting FP32 (single precision floating point operations), workstation compatible),
- Nvidia L40S (Ada Lovelace architecture, officially supporting FP32, equipped in a cluster),
- Nvidia H100 NVL (Hopper architecture, officially supporting FP64 (double precision floating point operations), equipped in a cluster).

As only one of them officially supports double precision floating point operations, a first step consisted in assessing the absence of bias in each case. For that purpose, the spatial distribution of the flux (integrated over the whole energy spectrum) was computed in four cases for a reflected 17x17 PWR assembly:

- while performing SIGMA1 on Nvidia L40S,
- while performing SIGMA1 on H100 NVL,
- while performing SIGMA1 on CPU,
- using pretabulated nuclear data.

In all four cases, the number of particles and active batches was set so that the relative uncertainty of the spatial neutron flux was less than 0.5% in each bin. The flux was tallied over a 17x17x14 mesh (with a pitch of 1.26 x 1.26 x 1 cm).

To assess the presence of any significant difference between two estimated averages, the following comparisons rely on the t -statistics defined as

$$t(i) = \frac{\bar{\phi}_1(i) - \bar{\phi}_2(i)}{\sqrt{s_1^2(i) + s_2^2(i)}} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\phi}_1(i)$ and $s_1(i)$ are the estimated mean flux and its associated estimated uncertainty in the spatial bin i for the first case, while $\bar{\phi}_2(i)$ and $s_2(i)$ are their equivalent for the second case with which the comparison is made.

Since spatially distributed quantities are computed, it is possible to build a histogram for the t -statistics (in which each realization corresponds to a specific location or energy). The histogram should be relatively close to a Gaussian distribution of mean 0 and standard deviation 1 if no bias is introduced between the two compared cases (due to the Central-Limit Theorem).

Figure 1 displays the histogram and the spatial distribution of the t -statistic for the spatially distributed neutron flux. The relative good agreement between empiric distributions and the Gaussian distribution, as well as the absence of spatial pattern, indicate that no bias seems to have been introduced by the on-the-fly Doppler broadening, whether it was performed on CPU, a FP64 GPU or a FP32 GPU.

The absence of bias in the FP32 case is due to the fact that the L40S (Ada Lovelace architecture) supports double-precision (FP64) operations, but at a significantly reduced rate compared to its FP32 throughput (a ratio of 1:64) [5].

(a) Verification against Pretabulated case (histogram)

(b) L40S vs Pretabulated (over space)

(c) H100 NVL vs Pretabulated (over space)

(d) CPU vs Pretabulated (over space)

Figure 1. *t*-statistics distributions regarding spatial distribution of the neutron flux.

4. PARAMETRIC STUDY

The main topic of this work has been conducting a parametric study to study the performance of the SIGMA1 algorithm on GPU for various sets of settings. The modeled system is still a 17x17 reflected PWR assembly, but here nuclides were added as traces, to increase the number of tasks sent on the GPU without modifying the physical behavior. The final compositions include about 550 nuclides (but only the ones relevant to a fresh PWR assembly have an impact on the physical behavior).

Due to technical limitations, the following results were obtained using a workstation equipped with a *Nvidia RTX A5000* (Ampere architecture, officially supporting FP32). As for the L40S GPU, double precision calculations are also available on the *Nvidia RTX A5000* but at a lower rate than single precision operations.

User accessible settings related to the use of a GPU for on-the-fly Doppler broadening in TRIPOLI-5 include:

- `schedule_size`: the number of particles in a batch that are followed in an *event based* manner (if set to 1, the simulation is run in a *history based* fashion).
- `offload_size`: the number of SIGMA1 computation tasks that are to be offloaded to the GPU for processing. A computation task is a triplet consisting of a nuclide, a particle energy, and a material temperature.
- `gpu_rate`: the rate at which GPU resources are utilized. This is a value between 0 and 1, where 0 means no GPU usage and 1 means full GPU usage.

The number of CPU threads used during other parallel stages of the simulation was added to this list to complete the following parametric study. Table I shows the sets of values used in the different simulations presented below. The `gpu_rate` was set to 1 for all simulations, which means that only the GPU was used to perform on-the-fly Doppler broadening.

Setting	Values
<code>cpu_threads</code>	2, 4, 8, 16, 24
<code>schedule_size</code>	$10^2, 10^3, 10^4, 10^5$
<code>offload_size</code>	$10^2, 10^3, 10^4, 10^5$
<code>gpu_rate</code>	1

Table I. Values used for the parametric study on simulation performances regarding on-the-fly Doppler broadening on GPU in TRIPOLI-5.

The electrical energy consumption and GPU load were monitored every 2 seconds. The electrical energy consumption was measured directly from an Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) to which the workstation was connected. The total power consumption recorded during the simulation encompasses both the GPU's energy usage and the baseline power draw of the host system. This global measurement enables a fair comparison of distinct simulation configurations by accounting for all contributing factors rather than isolating the SIGMA1 computation alone. Consequently, the analysis highlights the overall performance improvement that can be expected across an entire simulation when Doppler broadening is carried out on a GPU. Finally, the simulation time was also monitored.

4.1. Impact of the number of CPU threads

The number of CPU threads obviously has an impact on performance metrics, such as the simulation wall clock time. The idea here is to assess its effect on the energy cost of a calculation but also to see how it interacts with other parameters related to the use of a GPU.

As seen in Figure 2, the number of CPU threads is highly anti-correlated to the computation time and energy consumption of simulations, and the results present a low dispersion according to other parameters. The high energy cost in cases where few CPU threads are used is most likely due to a basal power consumption of the computer that is maintained for a longer time due to the high simulation time induced by a low number of CPU threads.

From the same Figure, it appears that for a low number of CPU threads, the GPU does not seem to be efficiently used, as evidenced by the trend observed in GPU load. In the case of the Nvidia RTX A5000 used here, 16 CPU threads are sufficient to saturate the GPU for certain sets of offload size and schedule size values. As a reminder, this GPU is not optimized for double precision operations, and HPC dedicated GPU will most likely behave differently regarding this parameter. Further investigation on different GPUs will be necessary to assess the HPC capabilities of the implementation of the TRIPOLI-5 SIGMA1 algorithm.

Figure 2. Energy consumption (left), simulation time (center) and GPU load (right) as function of the number of CPU threads. Each point corresponds to a set of offload size and schedule size values (undifferentiated for now).

4.2. Impact of the offload size and schedule size

The offload size corresponds to the size of the buffer that is sent to the GPU for SIGMA1 computations. The fill rate of this buffer is affected by two parameters:

- the schedule size, which is the number of simultaneous events that are treated in event-based transport. For a low value, this parameter could be limiting in filling the buffer.
- the number of nuclides in the simulation. The more nuclides, the more SIGMA1 tasks to perform, and thus the faster the buffer might be filled for a given value of the schedule size. In this study, the number of nuclides in the system did not vary and was set to approximately 550 nuclides.

Figure 3 presents the several performance metrics: electrical energy consumption, simulation time, and GPU load as a function of the offload size for 16 and 24 CPU threads. The relation between the offload size and the GPU load appears to be linear, but anti-correlated. However, the effect of this parameter on the simulation time and energy consumption is not linear, despite showing a correlation, and the optimum seems to be around 10^3 , which is also the value for which the effect of the number of CPU threads is the most important. This might be due to complex behavior regarding memory usage and is expected to change for a different device. For the Nvidia RTX A5000 used here, the optimal value for the offload size seems to be around 10^3 . This value is expected to be GPU dependent, and further studies on HPC dedicated GPUs will be conducted to confirm this hypothesis.

Figure 3. Energy consumption (left), simulation time (center) and GPU load (right) as function of the offload size. Only cases with 16 or 24 CPU threads are displayed. Each point corresponds to a schedule size value (undifferentiated for now).

More detailed results are presented in Figure 4 when the number of CPU threads is set to 24. Here, simulations with schedule sizes equal to 2 and 10 were added since this parameter appeared to be

limiting in the configurations presented above, as suggested by the low variability that can be observed within the groups in Figure 3. It is interesting to note that the highest GPU rate is obtained when the schedule size is low (equal to 2 to be precise, which is the lowest value for event-based transport in TRIPOLI-5). Although the optimal offload size value remains 10^3 , the performance gap with higher values is reduced for a low schedule size. This effect is most likely attributable to the large number of nuclides present in the medium. To illustrate this, we deliberately introduced about 500 trace nuclides into the system, thereby inflating the number of SIGMA1 tasks. With a schedule size of 2 this yields a product of nuclides \times schedule size of roughly 10^3 , which corresponds to the optimal offload size identified for our GPU.

The additional overhead observed when employing schedule sizes larger than this optimum may stem from complex GPU-memory-transfer dynamics; at present we have no definitive explanation for this behaviour. Once again, further studies on GPUs with different optimal offload sizes will provide more clues to validate these hypotheses.

Figure 4. Energy consumption (left), simulation time (center) and GPU load (right) as function of the offload size in the case with 24 CPU threads.

Measurements of the impact of the number of nuclides will be part of future work on this topic.

5. CONCLUSION

This study presented preliminary results on the performance of the GPU implementation of the SIGMA1 algorithm for on-the-fly Doppler broadening in TRIPOLI-5. The investigation confirmed that GPU-based execution does not introduce an observable bias in neutron flux calculations, even on FP32-optimized devices. The parametric study revealed that the number of CPU threads is the most influential factor on simulation performance, followed by the GPU offload buffer size, which affects both runtime and energy consumption in a non-linear manner. The number of events handled in event-based transport showed a secondary influence, primarily through its effect on GPU load saturation. These results demonstrate the feasibility of using GPUs to accelerate on-the-fly Doppler broadening, though further performance characterization on HPC-class GPUs with higher double precision floating point operation throughput is required. The study shows that the optimal number of tasks dispatched to the GPU — referred to here as the offload size — is not simply the maximum attainable value. Its optimum is supposed to be hardware-dependent. When the offload size is set above this optimum, increasing the number of particles processed simultaneously in the event-based tracking (i.e., the schedule size in this work) can noticeably degrade performance. Future work will focus on extending this study to systems with varying nuclide compositions and on refining GPU scheduling strategies on different hardware to validate our hypotheses and maximize performance on heterogeneous architectures.

Further investigation will also include comparisons with simulations in which Doppler broadening is performed on CPU and with pretabulated data based simulations. These studies will also include casting all double precision floating point operations into single precision floating point operations in

the SIGMA1 algorithm to assess the potential bias and optimization opportunities of single precision optimized GPUs.

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